

CRACK PROPAGATION PROPERTIES OF GFRP LAMINATES UNDER ACID STRESS ENVIRONMENT

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this study is to clarify crack propagation properties of woven GFRP laminates under stress corrosion cracking (SCC) conditions. The crack propagation behaviors and the threshold stress intensity factors K_{ISCC} for the stress corrosion cracking are determined by the constant loading tests and the cyclic loading tests. In the cyclic loading tests, it is possible to exclude effects of the frequency and the stress ratio on crack propagation behaviors in the $K_{I_{max}}-da/dt$ diagram under the environmental condition (1mol/l, 303K), and it is suggested that the crack propagation behavior depends on $K_{I_{max}}$ and time. As for an acid concentration, there is a conspicuous difference in crack propagation between the cyclic and the constant loading conditions. For any concentration of the acid, the cyclic crack-propagation rate is slower than the constant one under the solution temperature of 303K. Based on fractographic observations, it is found that micro-mechanisms of the crack propagation of both loading conditions are different, and fiber-matrix interfacial debondings are remarkable under the cyclic loading condition.

KEYWORDS: GFRP Laminates, Stress Corrosion Cracking, Stress Intensity Factor, Threshold, Stress Ratio, Frequency and Environmental Condition

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics have been used for a variety of chemical applications, since they have an outstanding performance as structural membership materials. However, there is a well-known fact that the glass fiber suffers from chemical attacks in corrosive environments even in composite material systems, and that such damage is accelerated by stress. The degradation mechanism in the GFRP due to stress corrosion, from the point of reliability, needs to be solved. In the last decade, a large number of studies have been done on characteristics of the stress corrosion cracking (SCC) in the GFRP.

Some studies on crack propagation behavior of the SCC in the GFRP have been reported in terms of linear fracture mechanics[1-5]. The rate of crack propagation depends on the applied stress and the corrosive environments. The clarification of the crack propagation behaviors

enable us to predict the residual life of structures and to establish the threshold stress intensity factor as the design criteria of GFRP structures. However, there has been almost no study on an evaluation of the threshold so far. Although many studies of SCC in the GFRP have been conducted under constant loading conditions, a study on the cyclic loading considered as the loading pattern for the practical structure under corrosive conditions has not been conducted. The objective of this study is to clarify the crack propagation properties in woven GFRP laminates under an acid stress environment, the threshold properties of the crack propagation, and the effect of loading conditions on properties of the crack propagation and the threshold.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Specimens are made from E-glass fibers in woven cloth with an epoxy resin by the hand layup method. The specimens are of the WOL type (Fig. 1) and material properties of specimens are shown in Table 1. The loading direction coincides with the warp strand one.

The specimens are tested by cyclic loading and constant loading tests under an acid environment. HCl was used as the acid solution. First, effects of the frequency on the crack propagation behavior in the cyclic loading tests are investigated. Various frequencies under the same environmental condition shown in Table 2 is tested. Next, effects of the stress ratio in the cyclic loading tests are examined. Three different stress ratios are adopted. Then results of the cyclic loading and the constant loading tests are compared, and clarified the effects of loading conditions, constant or cyclic (stress ratio $R=0.1$, 1.0Hz), under some environmental conditions shown as Table 3. A traveling microscope is used for the direct measurement of the

Fig. 1: Geometry of specimens.

Table 1: Material properties of specimens.

Specimen	E/Epoxy
Glass fiber	E-glass
Resin	Epoxy
Volume fraction of fiber %	32.0±2
Tensile strength MPa	277
Young's modulus GPa	17.7
Poisson's ratio	0.159

Table 2: Loading conditions.

	Constant	Cyclic					
		(changing frequency)			(changing stress ratio)		
Acid condition	HCl 1mol/l 303K						
Frequency Hz	-	0.01	0.1	1	5	1	
Stress ratio	-	0.1			0.1	0.4	0.7

Table 3: Environmental conditions.

Loading condition	Constant							Cyclic $R=0.1$ 1Hz				
Acid concentration mol/l	0.1	0.5	1	1.5	2	3	6	0.1	0.5	1	2	6
Acid temperature K	303											

crack length, and the crack-propagation rate is calculated from the relation between time and crack length. Stress intensity factor, K_I , is calculated by using FEM. After the tests, fractographic observations are conducted for each specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typical crack propagation behavior

The typical crack propagation behavior under constant loading condition is shown in a K_I - da/dt diagram in Fig. 2. The behavior is separated by a stable crack propagation region (Stage II) according to Paris's power law, and a low K_I region (Stage I) in which the crack propagation is converged.

The characteristic fracture surface peculiar to the stress corrosion cracking is observed. In the stable crack propagation region, a mirror zone, which is a trace of fiber corrosion, leads to a hackle and a river line which is an unstable failure of a fiber and matrix resin. The propagating directions of corrosion in the mirror zones are all the same with the macroscopic crack propagating directions. In the low K_I region, the fracture surface of a fiber completely consists of the mirror zone and polygonal lines on the fracture surface of a matrix are observed, which are peculiar to the low K_I region. Considering the circumstance mentioned above, it is suggested that the fracture surfaces change corrosive to mechanical with an increase of the stress intensity factors.

On the other hand, the typical crack propagation behavior under cyclic loading condition is shown in the ΔK_I - da/dN diagram in Fig. 3. The behavior is separated by the stable crack propagation region (Stage II) and the low K_I region (Stage I), same as under the constant loading conditions.

The fracture surface is quite different from the one under the constant loading condition. Fiber-matrix interfacial debondings and pull-out of fibers are remarkable in both regions. In the stable crack propagation region, the mirror zones

Fig. 2: Typical crack propagation behavior under constant loading condition.

Fig. 3: Typical crack propagation behavior under cyclic loading condition.

are located next to the interfacial debondings, so that it is considered that an initiation of the interfacial debondings contribute greatly to the crack propagation. The fracture surfaces change corrosive to mechanical as in the case of the static loading conditions.

The effects of the frequency and the stress ratio on the crack propagation behaviors

The effects of the frequency on crack propagation under the cyclic loading conditions are macroscopically conspicuous in evaluating the crack-propagation rate per cycle, da/dN (Fig. 4(a)), under the environmental condition (1mol/l, 303K). On the other hand, the effects are able to be minimized in evaluating the crack-propagation rate per second, da/dt (Fig. 4(b)). It is suggested that the crack propagation does not depend on a cycle, but on a time.

(a) A evaluating the da/dN . (b) A evaluating the da/dt .

Fig. 4: Macroscopic and microscopic effects of the frequency under cyclic loading condition.

(a) A evaluating the ΔK_I . (b) A evaluating the $K_{I_{max}}$. (c) the effect on fracture surfaces.

Fig. 5: Macroscopic and microscopic effects of the stress ratio under cyclic loading condition.

The effects of the frequency on the fracture surfaces are remarkable as shown in Fig. 4(c). A great number of pull-outs of fibers and unevenness are observed on the fracture surface under high frequency conditions. It is a noteworthy phenomenon that an increase of the frequency makes the number of pull-outs remarkable, although relations between the crack propagation rate (da/dt) and the ΔK_I almost coincide regardless of the frequency in the range of this study.

It is found that the differences of the fracture surfaces are striking as a function of the stress ratio in evaluating the stress intensity range, ΔK_I (Fig. 5(a)), under the environmental conditions (1mol/l, 303K). However, it is possible to minimize the effect in evaluating the $K_{I_{max}}$ (Fig. 5(b)). And an alternation of the stress ratio makes differences in the fracture surface remarkable as shown in Fig. 5(c). A great number of pull-outs of fibers and unevenness are observed on the fracture surface under the low stress ratio conditions as it is in the case of high frequency.

Considering the circumstances mentioned above, it is possible to exclude effects of the frequency and the stress ratio on the crack propagation behaviors in the $K_{I_{max}}-da/dt$ diagram. This provides a comparison between the results of the cyclic loading tests and the results of the constant loading tests in $K_{I_{max}}-da/dt$ diagram under the environmental conditions (1mol/l, 303K) (Fig. 6), and there is little difference on the macroscopic crack propagation behavior between constant loading tests and cyclic loading tests.

The effects of the environmental conditions

It is found that there is little difference between the macroscopic crack propagation behaviors of the constant and the cyclic loading tests under the environmental conditions (1mol/l, 303K) as mentioned above. However, with the change of the acid concentration, the effects of the environmental conditions on these relationship between the crack propagation behaviors are obvious. The K_I-da/dt diagram in the constant loading tests under several environmental conditions shown in Fig. 7(a). The crack propagation behaviors depend on the acid concentration conspicuously at the low K_I region. Therefore, the case of the cyclic loading condition is also obvious at the low K_I region (Fig. 7(b)). The crack-propagation rate under the cyclic loading condition is slower than that under the constant loading condition for various acid concentrations at the stable crack propagation region.

As for the threshold stress intensity factor $K_{I_{SCC}}$ under the constant loading condition and the threshold maximum stress intensity factor $K_{I_{maxSCC}}$ under the cyclic loading condition (R=0.1, 1Hz), both have strong dependence on the acid concentration as shown in Fig. 8. As the acid concentration increases, the $K_{I_{SCC}}$ seems to be a constant in the range of this study. It is noted that the $K_{I_{maxSCC}}$ takes its minimum value at 1mol/l. Differences between the $K_{I_{maxSCC}}$ and the $K_{I_{SCC}}$ depend on the acid concentration. The $K_{I_{maxSCC}}$ is larger than the $K_{I_{SCC}}$ without at the concentration, 1mol/l.

Fig. 6: A comparison of the crack propagation behaviors under the cyclic loading condition and the constant one.

From fractographic observations, there is no conspicuous obvious on fracture surfaces at the K_{ISCC} under the constant loading condition for various acid concentration. However, under the cyclic loading condition, interfacial crackings are remarkable in the higher concentration of the $K_{ImaxSCC}$ (Fig. 9). The interfacial crackings are most conspicuous at the environmental condition of 2mol/l, 303K. It is noted that there are no interfacial crackings at 0.1mol/l, 303K even in the cyclic loading condition. It is suggested that the interfacial crackings due to the chemical attack initiates, and it might be considered that the interfacial debondings have a relationship with a phenomenon that the values of the $K_{ImaxSCC}$ takes its minimum value at 1mol/l.

(a) Under constant loading conditions. (b) Under cyclic loading conditions.
 Fig .7: Crack propagation properties for various acid condition.

Fig. 8: K_{ISCC} and $K_{ImaxSCC}$ for various acid concentration under solution temperature of 303K.

(a) 0.1 mol/l, 303K (b) 2 mol/l, 303K (c) 6 mol/l, 303K
 Fig. 9: Fracture surface for various acid concentration at low K_I region under cyclic loading condition.

CONCLUSION

The crack-propagation behaviors and the threshold stress intensity factors K_{ISCC} for the stress corrosion cracking under both constant and cyclic loading tests are clarified. The effects of the frequency and the stress ratio of applied stress is minimized macroscopically in the $K_{I_{max}}-da/dt$ diagram, and it is considered that the crack propagation depends on the $K_{I_{max}}$ and time. As for acid concentration, there is a obvious deference in the crack propagation between the cyclic and the constant loading tests. In any concentration, the cyclic crack-propagation rate is slower than the constant one under solution temperature of 303K. The K_{ISCC} under the constant loading condition are larger than $K_{I_{max}SCC}$ under the cyclic loading condition at any acid concentration. As the acid concentration increase, the K_{ISCC} seems to be a constant. The $K_{I_{max}SCC}$ takes its minimum value at 1 mol/l. Based on a fractographic observation, micro-mechanisms of crack propagation of both loading conditions are different, and the fiber-matrix interfacial debondings are remarkable under the cyclic loading condition.

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